

Preparation and Properties of Substituted *o*-Chloro- and *m*-Chlorophenylhydroxylamines

(Miss) GOPIKA D. MEHD and YADVENDRA K. AGRAWAL

Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Technology and Engineering, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 001

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Eight new hydroxamic acids are synthesized for possible analytical applications. Physico-chemical properties, ionization constants, thermal stability and chemical stability of the acids have been determined.

HYDROXAMIC acids are versatile analytical reagents and widely used in organic and inorganic analysis¹⁻⁸. Preparation and properties of eight new hydroxamic acids derived from *o*-chloro- and *m*-chlorophenylhydroxylamines are described here. The procedure for preparation is based on the Schotten-Baumen technique⁶⁻⁸ and is successfully adopted for preparing *N*-arylhydroxamic acids derived from long chain aliphatic carboxylic acids. The hydroxamic acids prepared are characterised by their m.p., elemental analysis and ir spectral data. Preliminary studies show that these acids form chloroform extractable violet complex with vanadium(V) in conc. hydrochloric acid solution. Physical properties of these acids are given in Table 1.

All the hydroxamic acids are white crystalline solids, except the compounds derived from fatty acids which are yellow in colour and amorphous. The yields are generally 50-90%. The purity of the acids was ascertained by tlc, colorimetry and potentiometry and was found to be 98%. They are readily soluble in organic solvents like chloroform, dioxane, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, alcohol and are insoluble in water. They are stable to heat and light. All the acids give a violet colour extract with

vanadium(V) in chloroform from conc. hydrochloric acid (Table 2).

The *o*-chlorophenyl substituted acids are generally difficult to prepare and give low yields. All attempts to isolate *o*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine as a solid failed, hence the brown oily product was extracted with ether⁹.

Thermal stability tests show that these hydroxamic acids are very stable compounds (more than 8 hr). They are stable in HCl (6 *M*) and HClO₄ (6 *M*) at 50°. The degradation rate is of 1st order while with HNO₃ (0.8 *M*) they decompose and the rate is of 2nd order.

In the ir absorption spectra, only ν O-H, ν C=O and ν N-O bands, which are associated with the hydroxamic acid functional group, I, have been assigned.

TABLE 1—PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF *N*-ARYLHYDROXAMIC ACIDS

Compd. No.	Hydroxamic acids	Mol. formula	Mol. wt.	m.p. °C	Yield %	IR spectra frequency cm ⁻¹			UV spectra		Analysis%, Found/(Calcd.)		
						ν O-H	ν C=O	ν N-O	λ_{\max}	10 ⁻⁴ ε	O	H	N
1.	<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl- <i>o</i> -chlorobenzo-	C ₁₃ H ₉ NO ₂ Cl ₂	282.14	144	50	3200	1640	840	260	1.3	55.34	3.22	4.96
2.	<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl-myristo-	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₂ Cl	353.94	86	68	3180	1630	900	257	1.5	67.87	9.11	3.96
3.	<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl-palmito-	C ₂₃ H ₃₁ NO ₂ Cl	381.04	101	70	3160	1630	905	158	1.3	69.17	9.50	3.67
4.	<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl-stearo-	C ₂₇ H ₄₁ NO ₂ Cl	410.05	96	70	3180	1630	905	257	1.4	70.30	9.83	3.42
5.	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl- <i>o</i> -chlorobenzo-	C ₁₃ H ₉ NO ₂ Cl ₂	282.14	136	58	3120	1640	940	265	1.0	55.34	3.22	4.96
6.	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-myristo-	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₂ Cl	353.94	99	71	3160	1630	905	257	1.4	67.87	9.11	3.96
7.	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-palmito-	C ₂₃ H ₃₁ NO ₂ Cl	381.04	100	93	3160	1630	905	260	0.9	69.17	9.50	3.67
8.	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl-stearo-	C ₂₇ H ₄₁ NO ₂ Cl	410.05	95	80	3180	1630	905	259	1.1	70.30	9.83	3.42

Experimental

Materials and apparatus : Infrared spectra were recorded in the 2 to 15 μ region on a Perkin Elmer Model 221 spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics and calibrated by standard methods. Solids were dried over P₂O₅, finely powdered in an agate mortar and examined as KBr pellets or mulls in Nujol. The pH measurements were made on Elico digital pH meter equipped with glass and saturated calomel electrodes. The acid chlorides were prepared by the action of thionyl chloride on the corresponding acids and were vacuum distilled.

***N*-*o*-Chlorophenyl- and *N*-*m*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine :** These were freshly prepared by the reduction of *o*-chloro- and *m*-chloronitrobenzene, respectively, with zinc dust and ammonium chloride in aqueous-alcoholic solution. All attempts to isolate *o*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine as a solid failed and hence it was used *in situ*. The preparation for *N*-*m*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine⁹ is briefly described because it has been isolated as a solid, m.p. 95°, for the first time and the optimum conditions for maximum yield were established after repeated work.

A mixture of *m*-chloronitrobenzene (12.5 g), ethanol (25 ml), water (40 ml) and ammonium chloride (2.0 g) was stirred mechanically and treated with zinc dust (15 g) in small quantities (1-1.5 g) during the course of 25-30 min. The reaction temperature was maintained between 55 and 60° throughout, and stirring was continued for another 15 min. While hot, the zinc oxide was filtered and washed with 3 × 10 ml of hot ethanol. On the addition of about 400 g of ice to the filtrate a white product was obtained, which on crystallization from benzene and petroleum ether gave white cubes, yield 85%, m.p. 95°.

All the hydroxylamines were prepared by the above procedure. All hydroxamic acids were synthesized by the procedure described below.

A typical preparation of *N*-*m*-chlorophenyl-palmitohydroxamic acid is given below :

Freshly purified *N*-*m*-chlorophenyl hydroxylamine (5.0 g ; 0.035 mole) dissolved in cold diethyl ether (25 ml) and a fine suspension of sodium carbonate (6.0 g ; 0.057 mole) in water (30 ml) were taken in a 450 ml filtration flask fitted with a dropping funnel by B-19 joints, and stirred with magnetic stirrer. After the mixture was externally cooled to 0° or below, palmitoyl chloride (8.0 g ; 0.03 mole) dissolved in diethyl ether (50 ml) was added dropwise in course of 30 min and stirring was continued for 15 min. The reaction mixture was always kept alkaline. A yellowish product separated. The light yellow ethereal layer was separated and on vacuum

distillation yielded a yellow solid which was combined with the bulk of the product. The product was thoroughly triturated in a glass mortar with an excess of saturated sodium bicarbonate solution to remove the acidic impurities, filtered, washed with water and dried. The product was crystallized from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether. The yield of once crystallized product was 93%, m.p. 100°.

Colorimetric test : The well known coloured reaction occurring in 6 *M* HCl between vanadium(V) and hydroxamic acid was adopted². A known volume of vanadium(V) solution (5 ml ; 10⁻³*M*) was transferred into a 60 ml separatory funnel and molarity of HCl was adjusted to 6 *M* in a total volume of 20 ml by adding conc. hydrochloric acid. 5 ml hydroxamic acid solutions (in chloroform) was added and the contents were shaken vigorously. The violet extract was separated, diluted to 25 ml with chloroform and absorbance was measured at 515 nm against reagent blank. The concentration of hydroxamic acid was computed from a standard calibration curve. The colour of the extract and maximum absorbance for the hydroxamic acids is given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA ON HYDROXAMIC ACIDS

Compd. No.	Vanadium extraction			Thermal stability at 80° hrs	Mol. wt. Potentiometrically	pK _a
	Colour	λ_{\max}	Molar absorptivity l. mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹			
1.	V	530	4.4 × 10 ³	10	282.6	12.58
2.	RV	510	4.5 × 10 ³	10	352.5	13.62
3.	RV	515	4.6 × 10 ³	8	382.0	13.58
4.	RV	515	4.6 × 10 ³	8	410.5	13.71
5.	V	535	3.9 × 10 ³	10	282.6	12.44
6.	RV	515	4.9 × 10 ³	10	353.1	13.74
7.	RV	520	4.9 × 10 ³	10	381.4	13.52
8.	RV	515	4.7 × 10 ³	10	410.70	13.60

V = Violet, RV = Reddish violet,

Potentiometric tests : A known quantity of hydroxamic acid (0.25 g) was dissolved in 50 ml dimethylformamide and titrated with 0.1 *M* sodium methoxide using platinum and calomel electrode (saturated KCl in methanol) in an atmosphere of nitrogen. It was observed that these acids could be titrated potentiometrically with good accuracy. The molecular weights thus calculated are given in Table 2.

Chemical stability : 0.1 *M* solutions of hydroxamic acid in 6 *M* HClO₄, 6 *M* HCl or 0.8 *M* HNO₃ were kept in a thermostatic bath at 50 ± 0.1° and the hydroxamic acid was determined colorimetrically at regular intervals. The data are given in Table 2.

Thermal stability : 0.5 ml of 0.1 *M* chloroform solution of hydroxamic acid was transferred into fifteen 25 ml volumetric flasks. After evaporation of the chloroform under vacuum, the flasks were heated (80°) in a thermostated oven. The remaining hydroxamic acid was determined colorimetrically at regular intervals.

Ionization constants : These were determined at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in 70% dioxane-water medium (Table 2). The method for calculation of ionization constant was the same as described elsewhere¹.

The ionization of hydroxamic acid (HA) in aqueous solution gives hydrogen ion and hydroxamate ion and the equilibrium constant may be

$$K_{a(aq)} = \frac{[H^+][A^-]}{[HA]} \quad \dots (i)$$

$$\text{or } pK_{a(aq)} = -\log [H^+] + \log [HA]/[A^-] - 2 \log Y_{\pm} \quad \dots (ii)$$

Assuming the activity coefficient of unionized acid as unity and the empirical correction for "medium effect" as suggested by Van Uitert and Haas¹⁰ as

$$-\log [H^+] = B + \log U_H^0 + \log Y_{\pm}$$

the final form of the equation for calculating the ionization constants in the dioxane-water mixture is

$$pK_a = B + \log U_H^0 + \log [HA]/[A^-] - \log Y_{\pm} \quad \dots (iii)$$

where B is the pH meter reading and $\log U_H^0$ is determined experimentally in 70% dioxane-water media at 35° ¹¹.

The hydroxamic acid (0.5 mmol) in 47.5 ml dioxane-water mixture (70 : 30) were placed in a three-necked titration vessel (thermostated at 35°) carrying a glass and a saturated calomel electrodes. Nitrogen gas, presaturated with carbonate free

water was passed through the mixture. The contents were titrated after 15 min adding 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium hydroxide (in 70 : 30 dioxane-water) in 0.5 ml aliquots and noting the highest appropriate drift-free reading (B) on the pH meter.

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